

Secondary Gallstone Ileus Due to Bouveret Syndrome: Case Report

María Guadalupe Nieblas Serrano¹, Sara Rebeca Alma Abarca Valdovinos², Sarahí Carrillo Barraza³, Miguel Aurelio Alvarado Echeverría⁴, Alvaro de Jesús León Barragán⁵, Miguel Ángel Ramírez Madrigal⁶, Axell Daniel Lugo Rodríguez⁷, Luis Alex Pellegrini Islas⁸

¹Hospital General Regional No.1 Ciudad Obregón, Sonora.

²ISSSTE Hospital General "General José María Morelos y Pavón".

³Hospital universitario Torreón / Universidad Autónoma de Coahuila.

⁴Universidad Autónoma de Chihuahua.

⁵Hospital Regional de Alta Especialidad ISSSTE Veracruz / Universidad Cristóbal Colón.

⁶Universidad Autónoma de Zacatecas, Hospital General Fresnillo Dr. José Haro Ávila.

⁷Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social, unidad médica de alta especialidad H. E. No. 71, Torreón, Coahuila.

⁸Hospital General Regional No.1 Ciudad Obregón, Sonora.

ABSTRACT

Bouveret syndrome is an uncommon variant of gallstone ileus, in which a gallstone migrates through a cholecystoduodenal fistula and lodges in the duodenal bulb or stomach, causing a high gastrointestinal obstruction. It accounts for less than 3% of all gallstone ileus cases and typically occurs in elderly patients with multiple comorbidities, being even rarer in young patients without significant clinical history. Symptoms include persistent nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, and oral intolerance, which can mimic other acute abdomen presentations and delay diagnosis. We present the case of a 45-year-old female patient who arrived at the emergency department with a six-day clinical picture characterized by abdominal distension, constipation, postprandial gastrobiliary vomiting, severe generalized abdominal pain (VAS 10/10), and oral intolerance. Physical examination revealed signs of peritoneal irritation, and imaging studies showed pneumobilia, air-fluid levels, and a stone in the distal ileum. Abdominal computed tomography confirmed the presence of gallstones, pneumobilia, a cholecystoduodenal fistula, and an obstructive stone. An urgent exploratory laparotomy was performed with extraction of the stone via enterolithotomy, primary closure of the enterotomy, fistula repair with a Graham patch, and open cholecystectomy of the remaining gallbladder portion. Postoperative evolution was satisfactory. This case highlights an atypical presentation of Bouveret syndrome in a young patient, as well as the importance of timely diagnosis and comprehensive surgical intervention in managing this rare condition.

KEYWORDS: Bouveret syndrome, gallstone ileus, cholecystoduodenal fistula, intestinal obstruction, enterolithotomy, cholecystectomy.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
30 May 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Gallstone ileus is an uncommon cause of mechanical intestinal obstruction, accounting for approximately 1–4% of general cases and up to 25% in the elderly. It occurs due to the migration of one or more gallstones into the digestive tract through a cholecystoenteric fistula, usually cholecystoduodenal, causing intestinal obstruction, commonly in the terminal ileum. An even rarer presentation

is Bouveret syndrome, first described in 1896 by Léon Bouveret, in which the stone impacts at the level of the duodenal bulb or proximal stomach, causing high gastric obstruction.

This entity represents less than 3% of all gallstone ileus cases and more frequently affects elderly women with a history of chronic gallstone disease, being unusual in young patients. The clinical picture is often nonspecific and subacute,

Secondary Gallstone Ileus Due to Bouveret Syndrome: Case Report

characterized by persistent vomiting, nausea, abdominal distension, and epigastric pain, complicating diagnosis and delaying treatment.

Diagnosis relies on high clinical suspicion and imaging studies, especially computed tomography (CT), which can identify the modified Rigler's triad: pneumobilia, intestinal obstruction, and visualization of the ectopic stone. Treatment may be endoscopic or surgical, depending on stone location, size, and patient clinical status.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 45-year-old female patient without significant medical history presented to the emergency department of a secondary care hospital with a six-day clinical course characterized by progressive abdominal distension, constipation, postprandial gastrobiliary vomiting (food content with bile), severe generalized abdominal pain (10/10 on visual analog scale), and total oral intolerance.

Directed anamnesis revealed no history of chronic degenerative diseases, prior surgeries, or hospitalizations for similar symptoms. However, she reported that during her last pregnancy nine years earlier, gallstones were detected via ultrasound, with no subsequent follow-up or specific treatment.

On admission, the patient was afebrile, conscious, oriented, and hemodynamically stable. Physical examination revealed a markedly distended abdomen with absent bowel sounds, signs of peritoneal irritation such as hyperesthesia, hyperalgesia, and positive rebound tenderness, as well as superficial and deep palpation pain predominantly in the right hypochondrium. Generalized tympanism was noted on percussion.

Laboratory tests and standing abdominal X-ray were requested. Findings included air-fluid levels in the small bowel and absence of gas in the rectum, along with visible pneumobilia, suggestive of gallstone ileus. However, direct visualization of a stone within the intestinal tract was not possible via X-ray.

Given the diagnostic suspicion, contrast-enhanced abdominopelvic computed tomography (CT) was performed, revealing a scleroatrophic gallbladder with residual stones, marked pneumobilia, dilated intestinal loops with multiple air-fluid levels, and a 4 x 5 cm stone in the distal ileum. **(Figure 1)** Additionally, a cholecystoduodenal fistula was identified in the first portion of the duodenum near the pylorus.

Figure 1. Abdominopelvic CT scan showing the presence of a stone at the level of the duodenum.

Based on clinical and radiological findings, the patient was taken for urgent exploratory laparotomy. During the procedure, a gallstone was found 30 cm proximal to the distal ileum, which was mobilized approximately 40 cm to facilitate extraction via longitudinal enterolithotomy. The extracted stone measured 4 x 5 cm, and the enterotomy was closed primarily.

Exploration of the upper gastrointestinal tract revealed a cholecystoduodenal fistula with a fistulous opening in the first portion of the duodenum, firmly adherent to the pylorus. During exposure, the fistula spontaneously ruptured with the release of a second stone measuring 4 x 3 cm, which was extracted without complications. The duodenal defect was repaired with primary closure and a Graham patch. **(Figure 2)**

Figure 2. Stone measuring approximately 4 x 5 cm in diameter, stone measuring approximately 4 x 3 cm.

The gallbladder was evaluated, found scleroatrophic with a remaining posterior portion. Open cholecystectomy of the remnant

portion was performed, achieving adequate hemostasis of the hepatic bed without additional intraoperative complications. The immediate postoperative course was uneventful, with progressive recovery of intestinal function and oral tolerance. The patient was discharged with outpatient follow-up by general surgery and gastroenterology.

DISCUSSION

Bouveret syndrome is an extremely rare form of gallstone ileus characterized by gastric or duodenal obstruction secondary to the migration of a gallstone through a cholecystoduodenal fistula. First described in 1896 by Léon Bouveret, it accounts for less than 3% of gallstone ileus cases and approximately 0.05% of all intestinal obstructions. The pathophysiology involves formation of a cholecystoenteric fistula due to chronic gallbladder inflammation, allowing stones to pass into the digestive tract. Most cases occur in women over 70 years with a history of untreated gallstones, making the presentation in young patients as in this case unusual.

Clinically, Bouveret syndrome manifests with symptoms of high intestinal obstruction: nausea, persistent vomiting, epigastric pain, oral intolerance, and abdominal distension. These nonspecific manifestations may delay diagnosis and treatment. In this case, the patient showed a progressive clinical picture with signs of acute abdomen which, together with radiological findings of pneumobilia, intestinal obstruction, and a stone in the distal ileum, confirmed gallstone ileus complicated with Bouveret syndrome. CT is considered the imaging modality of choice due to its high sensitivity and specificity in detecting Rigler's triad: pneumobilia, intestinal obstruction, and ectopic stone.

Regarding treatment, although endoscopic approaches have been described for Bouveret syndrome, they are successful

only in selected cases, mainly when the stone is accessible, smaller than 2.5 cm, and the patient is clinically stable. In this case, the presence of two large stones (4 x 5 cm in distal ileum; 4 x 3 cm in duodenum), a complicated fistula, and signs of severe intestinal obstruction mandated urgent surgical laparotomy.

Surgical management is controversial and may range from simple enterolithotomy to more complex procedures such as fistula closure and cholecystectomy, performed in one or two stages. In this case, given the patient's clinical stability and technical feasibility, a single-stage surgery was chosen, including intestinal stone extraction, duodenal fistula closure with a Graham patch, and cholecystectomy. This strategy aims to prevent future complications such as cholangitis, recurrence of gallstone ileus, or persistent fistulas. Some authors suggest this approach may increase postoperative morbidity, although its indication is justified in young patients without comorbidities and with good physiological reserve, as in this case.

This report is relevant due to the atypical presentation in a young woman without complicated biliary disease or comorbidities, highlighting the need to consider Bouveret syndrome and gallstone ileus in patients presenting with intestinal obstruction and a history of gallstones, regardless of age.

CONCLUSION

Bouveret syndrome remains an uncommon and challenging clinical entity, not only because of its low prevalence but also due to its variable presentation and diagnostic complexity, especially when occurring outside the classical epidemiological profile. In this case, the young patient without comorbidities and with overlooked gallstones underscores how a seemingly resolved or ignored pathology may progress to major complications.

This case clearly illustrates the importance of maintaining a broad clinical approach and not underestimating the value of

Secondary Gallstone Ileus Due to Bouveret Syndrome: Case Report

a detailed history, which can provide critical information to guide diagnosis. It also emphasizes the key role of imaging studies, particularly computed tomography, as an essential tool for diagnosing rare entities not always evident in simple radiographs or initial methods.

Therapeutically, the decision for a single-stage comprehensive surgical intervention was favored by the patient's clinical stability, age, and absence of significant risk factors. This approach allowed not only immediate resolution of the obstructive condition but also elimination of the primary disease focus and prevention of future complications. Although literature continues to debate the optimal surgical approach, individualizing treatment remains the cornerstone of therapeutic success.

Finally, this case reinforces the need to pay greater attention to the follow-up of patients with incidental gallstone diagnosis, especially in health systems with limited access to specialized care. Timely and preventive management of gallstones could avoid progression to complex entities such as Bouveret syndrome. Clinical case reports like this remain essential to enrich collective medical knowledge and promote more informed surgical practice based on direct and contextualized experience.

REFERENCES

- I. Cappell, M. S., & Davis, M. (2006). Characterization of Bouveret's syndrome: A comprehensive review of 128 cases. *The American Journal of Gastroenterology*, 101(9), 2139–2146. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1572-0241.2006.00723.x>
- II. Rodríguez Hermosa, J. I., Codina Cazador, A., Ruiz Bañobre, J., Roig García, J., Figa Francesch, M., & Acero Fernández, D. (2001). Gallstone ileus: presentation of 10 cases and literature review. *Cirugía Española*, 69(4), 224–229. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-739X\(01\)78474-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-739X(01)78474-8)
- III. Lassandro, F., Gagliardi, N., Scuderi, M., Pinto, A., Gatta, G., & Mazzei, M. A. (2004). Gallstone ileus: analysis of radiological findings in 27 patients. *European Journal of Radiology*, 50(1), 23–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrad.2003.10.017>
- IV. Ayantunde, A. A., & Agrawal, A. (2007). Gallstone ileus: diagnosis and management. *World Journal of Surgery*, 31(6), 1292–1297. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00268-007-9011-8>
- V. Mir, A., Shaikh, N. A., & Riaz, N. (2021). Bouveret's syndrome: A rare cause of gastric outlet obstruction. *Cureus*, 13(1), e12490. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.12490>
- VI. Dumonceau, J. M., Devière, J., & Delhayé, M. (2003). Endoscopic management of Bouveret's syndrome. *Gastrointestinal Endoscopy*, 58(3), 469–470. [https://doi.org/10.1067/S0016-5107\(03\)01780-6](https://doi.org/10.1067/S0016-5107(03)01780-6)
- VII. Qasaimeh, G. R., Bakkar, S., Jadallah, K., & Shatnawi, N. J. (2014). Bouveret's syndrome: An overlooked diagnosis. A case report and review of literature. *International Surgery*, 99(6), 819–823. <https://doi.org/10.9738/INTSURG-D-13-00142.1>
- VIII. Clavien, P. A., Richon, J., Burgan, S., & Rohner, A. (1990). Gallstone ileus. *British Journal of Surgery*, 77(7), 737–742. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bjs.1800770707>
- IX. Inukai, K. (2019). Gallstone ileus: A review. *BMJ Open Gastroenterology*, 6(1), e000344. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgast-2019-000344>
- X. Reisner, R. M., & Cohen, J. R. (1994). Gallstone ileus: a review of 1001 reported cases. *The American Surgeon*, 60(6), 441–446.
- XI. Caldwell, K. M., Lee, S. J., Leggett, P. L., Bajwa, K. S., Mehta, S. S., & Shah, S. K. (2018). Bouveret syndrome: Current management strategies. *Clinical and Experimental Gastroenterology*, 11, 69–75. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CEG.S152288>
- XII. Nakao, A., Okamoto, Y., Sunami, M., Fujita, T., Tsuji, T., & Takakura, N. (1999). The successful management of Bouveret's syndrome by endoscopic lithotripsy. *Gastrointestinal Endoscopy*, 50(4), 566–568. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-5107\(99\)70282-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-5107(99)70282-6)
- XIII. Halabi, W. J., Kang, C. Y., Ketana, N., Lafaro, K. J., Nguyen, V. Q., Stamos, M. J., & Imagawa, D. K. (2014). Surgery for gallstone ileus: A nationwide comparison of trends and outcomes. *Annals of Surgery*, 259(2), 329–335. <https://doi.org/10.1097/SLA.0b013e31828c87f7>
- XIV. Sharma, D., Shekhawat, N. S., Mogra, N., & Goyal, N. (2010). Bouveret syndrome: a rare presentation and management. *Saudi Journal of Gastroenterology*, 16(1), 48–50. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1319-3767.58767>
- XV. De Palma, G. D., Galloro, G., Siciliano, S., & Persico, G. (2001). Endoscopic diagnosis and treatment of Bouveret's syndrome. *Surgical Endoscopy*, 15(1), 89. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004640000309>